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Introduction

Data encoding is traditionally applied in industry to stabilize processing, transfer, storage and display of digital data against distortions. Well-known are the adding of redundant bits when transmitting a N-bit word, which allows the receiver to find out which bits have been inadmissibly changed by external influences and have to be corrected.

In this paper we consider encoding strategies being optimized for technical surveying tasks. To this purpose a large binary code word is fixed on the rigid body, which 3D-position and 3D-angular orientation has to be known. The measurement instrument analyses the shift, rotation and frequency changes of the code image (Figure 1).

Figure 1: 3D-motion of a coded stick. Analyzing the codepattern allows to determine the 3D spatial position and 3D-orientation of the stick.

There are special requirements for the barcode design. First the code should be sufficiently 'nervous', i.e. sensitive to small variations of the object position and orientation. Secondly it should be distortion insensitive for measurements in problematic environmental situations, and third fast decoding algorithms should be available comparable to the well-known Fast-Fourier transformation. Then position and orientation can be precisely determined even if dust and dirt particles contaminate the barcode on the object. Such properties are well known from optical holograms, where contaminated or broken parts still include the full object information, however with reduced resolution.

We explain in the following some use cases of actual industrial relevance: First the digital level, which revolutionized the classical optical surveying technique, followed by an interesting low-cost variant without any focusing mechanisms. The concept of accepting defocused code images is then applied to automatically calibrate optical surveying instruments in the factory and to calibrate in real-time modern micro-machining systems, where femtosecond laser beams are swept over workpieces with sub-micrometer accuracy for material ablation.

Noise Equivalent Quantity

The impact of system noise on the measurement data has to be minimized in all cases. To this purpose we consider

in the following the *Noise equivalent quantity* $Ne(m)$ of the measurement parameters m , which are the 3D-position and 3D-orientation values. The goal is to reduce the $Ne(m)$ by encoding techniques. A powerful method is to use a barcode with a sharp autocorrelation peak and to correlate the measured 2D-code image data with artificially generated, pseudo-measurement data from a reference model. The model parameters are numerically varied until the cross-correlation between real and virtual measurement data is optimally peaked¹. Details of this concept are presented in the Appendix.

Case 1: Digital Level for Geodetic Measurements

To automatically record the height profile of a terrain, a measuring rod of 2 - 4 m length is positioned at distances z between 1.5 m to 100 m away from the levelling instrument. The rod barcode (Figure 2) is imaged on a CCD-sensor array, where the distance z is obtained from the size of the code image (magnification) and the levelling height h from the code's vertical position on the sensor. Since the measurement evaluation is based on the correlation estimator concept (see Appendix), two major problems must be solved by the code design. The first one is that at closer distances only parts of the barcode pattern are visible on the sensor leading to an unfavorable small L value in equation (6) of the Appendix, while at larger distances the image of a code element becomes smaller than the pixel width of the sensor which leads to a reduced information density in equation (6). Both effects unfavorably increase the $Ne(h,z)$ values and, consequently, lead to a lower accuracy of the measurement data of h and z . This, however, could be avoided if the code pattern is designed as Fine-code with good correlation properties even for code fragments, which is the situation at closer distances. At larger distances the Fine-code should cluster to a new code, called Coarse-code with fewer elements, but again good correlation properties. This *code-in-code* strategy in geodesy was adapted by Leica from wavelet considerations in image processing.

The method is robust and accurate, and measurement runs with realistic data yield $Ne(\alpha)$ values of about one pixel/100 (rms). Typical industrial applications are to control the mechanical vibrations of bridges and their supporting pillars, the stability of huge cranes in strong winds, the loading of cargo containers, and the exact angular alignment of missiles, mortars and rockets at their launch pads.

Figure 2: Level Rod (Classical scaling, left) and Leica barcode (right)

¹ SPS Focus No 3: Chap. 5.1 Physics and Industries, https://sps.ch/en/publications/sps_focus

Case 2: Fix-Focus Digital Level

The power of processing encoded data and their efficient numerical decoding allows to further increase the performance of instruments in daily use. We demonstrated this first by an extension of the digital level eliminating focusing, and secondly by applying the idea to laser micro-machining. To this purpose we split the lens element located in the level's exit pupil in five segments of different optical power (i.e. focal length), adapted to the distances 2.5 m, 4.5 m, 8 m, 16 m and 40 m (Figure 3). Each lens segment includes a prism to shift its received code image to a different position on the 2D sensor. Dependent on the rod distance between 2 m and 100 m one always measures five more or less strongly blurred images of the code rod.

13.89 MM
Positions: 1-5
Scale: 1.80 BIM 19-Nov-01

Figure 3: Digital Level, where the last lens is split in five segments of different focusing power.

In Figure 4 we see from left to right the code images produced by the five lens segments fix-focused on 16 m, 8 m, 2.5 m, 4.5 m and 40 m. The actual rod distance is indicated in each sub-figure.

The simultaneous recording of five different blurred and different magnified code images allows to cross-correlate the individual code patterns. Even the totally blurred code image at rod distance of 3 m includes enough information to extract height and distance values. The results are as-

Figure 4: Five barcode images on the instrument's CCD for different rod distances between 3 and 80 m.

Figure 5: Results of levelling height h and distance z for different illumination profiles.

tonishingly good (Figure 5): accuracies of about 0.1 mm for the object height, and 1 mm to 4 mm for the object distance have been measured within the application-relevant distance range from 2 m to 18 m².

Case 3: Automatic Calibration of Optical Surveying Instruments

Surveying instruments like levels, theodolites, laser trackers must be precisely calibrated according to international certification standards. An interesting, fast and precise method is that the instrument under test looks inside a specially prepared digital level, focused at infinity and carrying in its focal plane a code plate of different glass thickness segments and barcodes of different size (Figure 7). The four segments correspond to the true focus situation at 1.5 m, 4 m, 10 m and 100 m. The instrument to be calibrated is automatically focused to any distance between 1 and 100 m and the four permanently recorded, but more or less unsharp code images are analyzed to verify the instrument's displayed distance value z with respect to its motor drive parameters.

² United States Patent Gaechter B., Braunecker B. US 6,081,327 A, Jun. 27, 2000 B

Figure 6: Rod at 9.6 m and illuminated by laser light. The data encoding concept minimizes the influence of speckle noise on the measurement accuracy.

Figure 7: The theodolite to be calibrated looks into the calibration instrument on four different code patterns, virtually located at 1.5 m, 4 m, 10 m and 100 m.

Case 4: In Field Control of Laser Macro/Micro-Machining

Material ablation by lasers is one of the most promising processing methods in industry due to its efficiency, accuracy and flexibility, and due to the fact that optical surface measurement by interferometers can be performed parallel at the same time within the same coordinate system. The whole material treating process takes place in a finite working volume (WV), into which the work piece is loaded by robots. A combination of a fast beam-deflecting unit (xy-scanner) and a fast vario-optic directs the laser focus to any point (x,y,z) inside the WV with μm accuracy (Figure 8).

The high pointing accuracy demands require the regular calibration of the motor drives of both optical control units. To this purpose a special target plate (TP) with code patterns of different size is permanently installed close to the bottom of the WV. The first step is to determine the correct position and the azimuthal orientation of the TP relative to the current control data of scanner and vario. To this purpose the

Figure 8: Target Plate TP with fine, medium and coarse code for WV calibration, together with reflecting spheres for TP installation purposes.

laser beam with reduced intensity is focused on the TP and swept along a line with known start and end points. (Figure 9a) The beam hits the code elements of a special shark-fin pattern in its left and right branches (blue points). The knowledge of the position of the hitpoints and their mutual distances allows to calculate the x,y coordinates of the TP center relative to the scan line and to readjust the TP if necessary. Later in daily work the method is applied to control the relation TP to scanning system, which is necessary after the laser, scanner or vario-optics were changed or after general service work.

The second step concerns the WV calibration in x,y,z. When the TP is optically accessible during a work piece change, the laser with reduced intensity is focused by the vario-optic to different z-planes within the WV and swept in x and y. Depending on the z-value the laser spot of variable diameter illuminates several codepattern of different size at the TP (Figure 9b). The code pattern are back-imaged through scanner and vario-optic on a sensor. Analysing the blurred code element positions and the size of the illumination profile allows to determine the x,y,z coordinates of the true laser focus as function of the motor drive parameters of scanner and optics.

Figure 9: a) Special code pattern is hit by the laser beam (blue) to re-adjust the Target plate. b) Linear code patterns of different size (small, medium and large) are radially distributed. The pattern of a) is located in the centre of the TP.

Summary

The examples show that optical remote sensing is a powerful technique which is widely applicable in industrial practice from the micrometer to the centimeter range. Since in all cases code label images are evaluated, no measurement errors can occur by mechanical contacts. The digital comparison of encoded label data with the model data by estimation algorithms can be easily adapted to many applications. The numerical evaluating of the code position, magnification, magnification chirp, distortion or blur parameters allows to determine the body's 3D position and 3D orientation in a flexible, fast, robust and cost-effective way.

Appendix

IMPROVING THE SIGNAL TO NOISE RATIO BY DATA ENCODING

The object, a rigid body as the cylindrical rod in Figure 2, is characterized by the parameter set $m = \{3D\text{-position}, 3D\text{-angular orientation}\}$. An optical system images the object on a 2D sensor, and the goal is to precisely determine the six parameters, even if the measurement data are corrupted by severe object and system noise. To this purpose one considers the *Noise equivalent quantity* $Ne(m)$ of the measurement data.

The goal is to reduce the $Ne(m)$ values by data encoding, thereby applying the so-called method of *correlation estimators* on the measurement data. The noisy image data are $Q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \equiv Q_0(\mathbf{x}, m_0) + N(\mathbf{x})$, with $\mathbf{x} = (x, y)$ the pixel coordinates on the CCD, where parameter m_0 describes the true, but unknown geometrical parameter set. Q_0 are the ideal, noiseless, but blurred code signals, and $N(\mathbf{x})$ denotes the noise intensity at pixel \mathbf{x} . The measurement signals are normalized:

$$q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \equiv (Q - \langle Q \rangle) / \sqrt{\int (Q - \langle Q \rangle)^2 d\mathbf{x}} \\ \equiv q_0(\mathbf{x}, m_0) + n(\mathbf{x})$$

with $n(\mathbf{x}) \equiv N(\mathbf{x}) / \sqrt{\int (Q - \langle Q \rangle)^2 d\mathbf{x}}$,

where $\langle \rangle$ describes the statistical expectation value. The integral over \mathbf{x} on the sensor is taken *along* the code pattern axes of length L , i.e. between $-L/2$ and $+L/2$. Therefore L counts the number of code elements or sensor pixels.

CORRELATION ESTIMATOR

The known normalized code reference function is $p(\mathbf{x}, m)$, where the start parameter m is chosen to be close to m_0 , and m is varied for optimum mathematical consistency between p and q . One considers the cross-correlation function across all code elements

$$c(\mathbf{x}, m, m_0) = \int q(\mathbf{x}', m_0) \cdot p(\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x}'. \quad (1)$$

Since the code pattern p should be designed so that its auto-correlation function is sharply peaked, the goal of the optimization process m to m_0 is to *maximize the peak of the cross-correlation function*

$$c_{peak}(\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}, m, m_0) = \int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (2)$$

One calculates its derivative with respect to m

$$c'_{peak} \equiv \delta c_{peak} / \delta m = \int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot \{ \delta p / \delta m \}(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x},$$

and also its variance. To this purpose one considers

$$c'_{peak} - \langle c'_{peak} \rangle = \int (n - \langle n \rangle) p' d\mathbf{x}$$

where biasfree and uncorrelated pixel noise $\langle n \rangle = 0$ and $\langle n(\mathbf{x}') n(\mathbf{x}'') \rangle = \sigma_n^2 \cdot \delta(\mathbf{x}' - \mathbf{x}'')$ is assumed. This results in the variance

$$\sigma_c^2 = \langle |c'_{peak} - \langle c'_{peak} \rangle|^2 \rangle \\ = \int \{ p'(\mathbf{x}', m) d\mathbf{x}' \} \cdot \int \{ p'(\mathbf{x}'', m) \langle n(\mathbf{x}') n(\mathbf{x}'') \rangle d\mathbf{x}'' \} \\ = \sigma_n^2 \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x}. \quad (3)$$

Next one needs the second derivative of the correlation function c''_{peak} , and develops c' at $m = m_0$ to get $c'_{peak}(m) = c'_{peak}(m_0) + \Delta m \cdot c''_{peak}(m_0) = \Delta m \cdot c''_{peak}(m_0)$, since $c'_{peak}(m_0) = 0$.

Then $\Delta m = c'_{peak}(m) / c''_{peak}(m_0)$ and its variance is

$$\sigma_m^2 = \langle \Delta m^2 \rangle = \sigma_c^2 / (c''_{peak})^2 \\ = \sigma_n^2 \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / (c''_{peak})^2 \\ = \sigma_n^2 \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / \left(\int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p''(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x} \right)^2 \\ = \sigma_n^2 / \langle Q \rangle^2 \cdot 1/L \\ \cdot \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / L / \left(\int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p''(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x} / L \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

and the *Noise Equivalent value of m*

$$Ne(m) \equiv \sigma_m = 1 / SNR \cdot CF, \quad (5a)$$

using $SNR \equiv \langle Q \rangle / \sigma_n$ and the code improvement factor

$$CF \equiv (1 / \sqrt{L}) \cdot \sqrt{\int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / L} / \\ \int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p''(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x} / L. \quad (5b)$$

CF depends on three factors: the length L of the recorded code pattern on the sensor, i.e. the number of code elements; second on a term with p' which can be interpreted as the *information density* of the blurred codefunction p , asking how sensitive the correlation peak reacts on changes of the variation of m , and finally on a term with p'' describing the sharpness of the code correlation peak c , i.e. its curvature c'' . When designing the code function p the derivatives p' and p'' must also be considered to effectively minimize $Ne(m)$ at all measurement situation.

The $Ne(m)$ can be better understood if one assumes $q \approx p$. Then the third term in (5b) reduces to

$$\int q(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p''(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x} / L \approx \int p(\mathbf{x}, m_0) \cdot p''(\mathbf{x}, m) d\mathbf{x} / L \\ = \{ p \cdot p'(L/2) - p \cdot p'(-L/2) \} / L - \left\{ \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / L \right\} \\ \approx \left\{ \int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / L \right\}$$

for large L , leading to the approximation

$$Ne(m) \approx 1 / \left\{ SNR \cdot \sqrt{L} \cdot \sqrt{\int p'(\mathbf{x}, m)^2 d\mathbf{x} / L} \right\}. \quad (6)$$

In conclusion $Ne(m)$ is minimized by a large SNR , by many recorded code elements (large L) and by a large *information density* of the code function, i.e. by a code of good 'nervousness'.